

Copper(II) Complexes of Isonitroso- β -Diketones

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ISONITROSOBENZOYLACETONE (HINBA), isonitrosodibenzoylmethane (HINDBM), *p*-chloroisonitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Cl-INBA) and *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Br-INBA) have earlier been employed as reagent in spectrophotometric determination of iron, palladium and ruthenium¹⁻⁴. In view of their importance as analytical reagents, it is desirable to study the physicochemical aspects of solid metal complexes. Structural investigations of Pd(II) and Co(III) complexes of HINBA and HINDBM have been reported earlier⁵. We describe here the synthesis of these ligands and characterization of their copper(II) complexes by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurement, uv, ir and nmr techniques.

Experimental

Synthesis of the ligands :

Isonitrosobenzoylacetone (HINBA, C₁₀H₈O₃N) / *p*-chloroisonitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Cl-INBA, C₁₀H₇O₃NCl) / *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Br-INBA, C₁₀H₇O₃NBr) : To a solution of 10 g benzoylacetone / *p*-chlorobenzoylacetone / *p*-bromobenzoylacetone in 31 ml glacial acetic acid is added aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (4.6 g NaNO₂ dissolved in minimum amount of water) dropwise with fast stirring and keeping the temperature at 10-15° for HINBA and <5° for *p*-Cl-INBA and *p*-Br-INBA ligands. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand for 1 to 2 hr at room temp., it is poured into ice water and cooled. The crystals are collected by filtration, washed with ice cooled water and recrystallized from methanol.

HINBA, m.p. 124-126°. (Found : C, 62.7 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 7.3. Calcd. C, 62.82 ; H, 4.7 ; N, 7.32%).

p-Cl-INBA, m.p. 160°. (Found : C, 53.0 ; H, 3.51 ; N, 6.2 ; Cl, 15.5. Calcd. C, 53.2 ; H, 3.54 ; N, 6.25 ; Cl, 15.7%).

p-Br-INBA, m.p. 164°. (Found : C, 44.3 ; H, 2.85 ; N, 5.1 ; Br, 29.5. Calcd. C, 44.47 ; H, 2.96 ; N, 5.18 ; Br, 29.6%).

Isonitrosodibenzoylmethane (HINDBM, C₁₅H₁₈O₃N) : 20 g dibenzoylmethane (Koch Light, England) is dissolved in about 40 ml chloroform and cooled to <0°. To this, 15 ml amyl nitrite and 2 ml alcoholic hydrochloric acid (1 ml ethanol + 1 ml conc. HCl) are added with fast stirring. The reaction mixture is allowed to stand for 2 hr and then extracted with 40 ml petroleum ether when white sandy crystals of the ligand separate out. The crystals are collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 146°. (Found : C, 71.00 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 5.5. Calcd. C, 71.2 ; H, 4.37 ; N, 5.53%).

Preparation of copper(II) complexes : An ammoniacal solution of copper chloride and an ethanolic solution of the ligand are mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio. To this mixture dilute solution of ammonium hydroxide is added dropwise till the olive green complexes precipitate out. The complexes are filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried under vacuum.

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were measured at room temp. (27°) by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as the calibrant. The electronic spectra of the complexes were taken on Beckman DU 2 spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra of the complexes in nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin Elmer IR recording spectrophotometer (Model 221) with KBr prism. The proton magnetic resonance spectra of the complexes in CDCl₃ were recorded on F. J. Varian spectrometers-100 MHz, using TMS as the standard. C, H and N were estimated by microanalytical methods.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) of the complexes corresponds to the molecular formula Cu(C₁₀H₁₀O₃N)₂.2H₂O, Cu(C₁₀H₈O₃NCl)₂.2H₂O, Cu(C₁₀H₇O₃NBr)₂.2H₂O and Cu(C₁₅H₁₈O₃N)₂.2H₂O. The complexes are insoluble in carbon tetrachloride and petroleum ether (60-80°) and very sparingly soluble in most of the organic solvents.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, UV AND MAGNETIC MEASUREMENTS OF CU-ISONITROSO- β -DIKETONE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Decom. Temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Magnetic moment B.M.	Electronic absorption bands (kK)	
			C	H	N	M		Methanol	Chloroform
1. Cu(INBA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Olive green	150	49.5 (50.1)	4.0 (4.17)	6.8 (5.89)	13.8 (13.25)	0.8	28.5	29.0
2. Cu(<i>p</i> -Cl-INBA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	148	37.8 (37.53)	3.5 (3.13)	5.0 (4.38)	10.5 (9.93)	0.9	27.7	28.5
3. Cu(<i>p</i> -Br-INBA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	187	42.9 (43.65)	3.2 (3.64)	5.5 (5.09)	12.1 (11.55)	1.08	28.9	29.4
4. Cu(INDBM) ₂ .2H ₂ O	"	194	58.9 (59.68)	3.7 (3.31)	4.1 (4.64)	10.8 (10.52)	1.14	28.9	28.9

